

PANEL DATA IN TOURISM DEMAND

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Abstract

This study has explained the construction of panel data models, compared the estimation performance of Fixed Effects and Random Effects models in application of tourism demand analysis. Our novelty model of panel data focuses on the 10 best travel destinations according to Tripadvisor award 2018 ($i=1,2,\dots,10$). We have considered the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for country i (Y_{it}) related to the number of international tourist arrivals in country i (X_1), International tourism receipts for country i (X_2), International tourism expenditures for country i (X_3), Tax revenue in tourism sector for country i (X_4) and Total employment in tourism sector for country i (X_5), for the period 1995 to 2017. After fulfilling all diagnostic tests in panel data and based on the principle of simplicity (Parsimony), we found that the most appropriate model is Fixed Effect model with Individual Effect ($\log Y_{it} = 0.42 \log X_1 + 0.17 \log X_2 + 0.54 \log X_3 - 0.75 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$) where the values of c_i (Unobservable Individual Effects) for each countries such as : Paris (1.776); UK(1.776); Italy(1.839); Indonesia(1.819); Greece(1.736); Spain(1.573); Czech Rep.(1.589); Morocco(1.717); Turkey(1.826) and USA(1.877) respectively. Furthermore, Adj. R-Squared = 0.95054 and F-statistic = 1103.48 (p-value = 2.22e-16 < 0.05), this implies that the Number of International Tourist Arrivals in country i (X_1), International Tourism Receipts for country i (X_2), International Tourism Expenditures for country i (X_3), and Total Employment in tourism sector for country i (X_5) are adjusted together explain Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for country i (Y_{it}) by 95.054% while the remaining 4.946% is explained by other variables outside the model.

Keywords: Fixed Effects Model; Random Effects Model; Unobservable Individual Effects.

1. INTRODUCTION

The phenomenal growth of both the world-wide tourism industry and academic interest in tourism over the last forty years has generated great interest in tourism demand modelling and forecasting from both business and academic sectors. Lim (1997) noted that, although time series data are widely utilized in estimating tourism demand, few studies use cross-section or panel data. As an overview, we can see in Romilly et al. (1998) used panel data to develop a model of international tourism spending using both economic and social variables for a total of 138 countries over 7 years. The use of the

data panel approach to identify the recent effects of demographic change on Japanese people's travel Propensity is also used by Sakai et al (2000). In the other hand, Ledesma-Rodriguez and Navarro-Ibanez (2001) estimated short-run and long-run elasticities for tourists visiting the Island of Tenerife. In addition, Naude & Saayman (2005) identified factors affecting tourist arrivals to Africa. Garin-Munoz (2006) and Garin-Munoz & Montero-Martin (2007) modeled international tourism demand for the Canary Islands and the Balearic Islands, respectively.

Some other interesting research that uses data panels in tourism demand we can see in Taylor & Ortiz (2009) examined whether climate change has impacted regional tourism in the UK. Brida & Risso (2009) studied the German demand for tourism in South Tyrol using dynamic panel data. Kuo et al. (2009) estimated the impact of Avian Flu on international tourist arrivals to Asian, European and African countries and Habibi et al. (2009) developed a panel data model of international tourism demand for Malaysia.

Hsiao (2003) and Baltagi (2013) lists several benefits of using panel data analysis, these include the following:

1. The use of panel data enables us to control for individual heterogeneity, Panels data Bring more sufficient informative data, then it impacts to be more variability, less collinearity among the variables, so that it comes to be more degrees of freedom and more effective and efficient
2. With the Panel data, one is better able to study the dynamics of adjustment.
3. The Panel data are more suitable for identifying and measuring effects that are simply not detectable in pure cross-section or pure time-series data.
4. The Panel data models allow us to construct and test a more complicated behavioral model than do pure cross-section or time-series data.
5. Micro panel data gathered on individuals, firms, and households can be measured more accurately than similar variables measured at the macro level. Biases resulting from aggregation over firms or individuals may be reduced or eliminated.
6. Macro panel data, on the other hand, have longer time series and, panel unit root tests have standard asymptotic distributions and do not suffer from the problem of nonstandard distributions encountered with unit root tests in time series analysis.

Panel data are most useful when we suspect that the outcome variable depends on explanatory variables that are not observable but correlated with the observed explanatory variables. Parameter estimation in regression analysis with cross-section data carried out with OLS estimation. This method will give the results of the estimation which is the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE) if all of the Gauss Markov assumptions are met including non-autocorrelation. When we are dealing with panel data, this last condition is certainly difficult to fulfill so that parameter estimation is no longer for BLUE. If panel data is analyzed by approaching time series models, then there is information on the variety of unit cross-sections that are ignored in modeling. One of the advantages of panel data analysis is considering the variety that occurs in unit cross-sections. The purpose of this study is to explain the parameter estimation of the panel data model with the approach of Fixed Effects Model and Random Effects Model, to find out the best model in panel data parameter estimation and to analyze the best model in panel data parameter estimates using diagnostic test criteria. This study

has explained proportionally the construction and estimation of Panel data models in an application to tourism demand analysis.

2. METHODOLOGY

Panel data are also known as cross-sectional time series data or longitudinal time series data is a dataset in which the behavior of entities is observed across time. These entities could be countries, individuals, companies, states, etc. In general, there are three-panel models that are often used, namely pooled regression model, the fixed-effects model and the random-effects model.

2.1 Pooled Regression Model

The equation for the Pooled Regression :

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (i=1,2,\dots,N; t=1,2,\dots,T) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$y_{i,t}$ is the dependent variable where i represents countries and t represents time. The i subscript, therefore, denotes the cross-section dimension, whereas t denotes the time-series dimension; $x'_{i,t}$ is vector of k -variables independent from entity- i and observed in the t -time period (i.e., there are k independent variables, where each variable is panel data); $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the error term, The error term is identical and independently distributed or iid $(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2)$ for all i and t . Estimates for this model can be done using the usual OLS (Ordinary least square) method. For the panel data model, it is often assumed that the effect of changes in X is assumed to be constant in time and cross-times category.

2.2 Fixed Effects Model

The pooled regression model can be rewritten, and then given additional constants components c_i and d_i

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + c_i + d_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (i = 1,2,\dots, N; t = 1,2,\dots, T) \quad (2)$$

Where,

c_i denotes the unobservable individual effect; d_i denotes the unobservable time effect. When contain c_i and d_i , is called a two-way fixed effect model, whereas if $d_i = 0$ or $c_i = 0$ called a one-way fixed effect model. If the number of observations is the same for all cross-time categories, the model is balanced and if on the contrary, it is imbalanced. For the one-way fixed effect model, it is often assumed that the component $d_i = 0$, which is owned by the model.

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

2.3 Random Effects Model

We can see the effects of various characteristics that are constant in time or constant between individuals by using random effect models. Random effect models are generally written as follows

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t} \beta_{i,t} + w_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

Where :

$$w_{i,t} = c_i + d_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (5)$$

With $c_i \sim \text{IID}(0, \sigma_c^2)$, $d_i \sim \text{IID}(0, \sigma_d^2)$ and $w_{i,t} \sim \text{IID}(0, \sigma_w^2)$ independent of each other

If component of d_i or c_i is assumed to be 0, it is called a model The One-Way Random Effect Model, whereas in other circumstances it is called The Two-Way Random Effect Model.

2.4. Generalized Least Squares

We can write $W_i = [w_{i1}, w_{i2}, \dots, w_{iT}]$ In view of this form of w_{it} , we have what is often called an “error components model” then, for this model,

$$E[w_{it}^2] = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2,$$

$$E[w_{it} w_{is}] = \sigma_u^2, t \neq s.$$

For the T observations for unit i, let $\Omega = E[w_i w_i']$. Then

$$\Omega = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \dots & \sigma_u^2 \\ \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \dots & \sigma_u^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 & \dots & \sigma_\varepsilon^2 + \sigma_u^2 \end{bmatrix} = \sigma_\varepsilon^2 I_T + \sigma_u^2 i_T i_T' \quad (6)$$

Where I is a T x1 column vector of 1s. Since observations i and j are independent, the disturbance covariance matrix for the full nT observations is

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} \Omega & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \Omega & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \Omega \end{bmatrix} = \Omega \otimes I_n \quad (7)$$

This matrix has a particularly simple structure.

For generalized least squares, we require $V^{-\frac{1}{2}} = I \otimes \Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ therefore, we need only find $\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, which is $\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \left[I - \frac{\theta}{T} i i' \right]$ Where $\theta = 1 - \frac{\sigma_\varepsilon}{\sqrt{T\sigma_u^2 + \sigma_\varepsilon^2}}$ the transformations of

y_i and X_i for GLS is therefore

$$\Omega^{-\frac{1}{2}} y_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \begin{bmatrix} y_{i1} - \theta \bar{y}_i \\ y_{i2} - \theta \bar{y}_i \\ \vdots \\ y_{iT} - \theta \bar{y}_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

And likewise for the rows of X_i . For the data set as a whole, generalized least squares is computed by the regression on these partial deviations of y_{it} on the same transformation of x_{it} . Note the similarity of this procedure to the computation in the LSDV model, which has $\theta = 1$. It can be shown that the GLS estimator is, like the OLS estimator, a matrix weighted average of the within and between units estimators:

$$\hat{\beta} = \hat{F}^W b^W + (I - \hat{F}^W) b^b \quad (9)$$

Where

$$\hat{F}^W = [S_{xx}^W + \lambda S_{xx}^b]^{-1} S_{xx}^W$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\sigma_\varepsilon^2}{\sigma_\varepsilon^2 + T\sigma_u^2} = (1 - \theta)^2$$

2.5. General Feasible Generalized Least Squares Models

The estimated error covariance matrix is $\hat{V} = I_n \otimes \hat{\Omega}$, with

$$\hat{\Omega} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\hat{u}_{it} \hat{u}_{it}^T}{n} \quad (10)$$

the error or mismatched covariance structure inside every group (if Effect="Individual") of observations to be fully unrestricted may be affected by this framework. Then, it against any kind of intragroup heterokedasticity and serial correlation. This structure is identified identically across groups and that general FGLS is inefficient under group wise heterokedasticity and Cross-sectional correlation is does not include a priori. Furthermore, the number of variance parameters to be estimated with $N = n \times T$ data points is $\frac{T(T+1)}{2}$, which makes these estimators particularly suited for situations where $n \gg T$.

2.6 Model Analysis

2.6.1 Hausman's Test

We can run a Hausman test to decide between fixed or random effects where the null hypothesis is that the preferred model is random effects vs. the alternative the fixed effects. It basically tests whether the unique errors (ui) are correlated with the regression, the null hypothesis is they are not. Hausman (1978) developed a test based on the idea that under the hypothesis of no correlation, both OLS in the LSDV model and GLS are consistent, but OLS is inefficient, whereas under the alternative, OLS is consistent, but GLS is not. Therefore, under the null hypothesis, the two estimates should not differ systematically, and a test can be based on the difference. The other essential ingredient for the test is the covariance matrix of the difference vector, $[b - \hat{\beta}]$:

$$Var[b - \hat{\beta}] = Var[b] + Var[\hat{\beta}] - Cov[b, \hat{\beta}] - Cov[b, \hat{\beta}]^T \quad (11)$$

Hausman's essential result is that the covariance of an efficient estimator with its difference from an inefficient estimator is zero, which implies that

$$Cov[(b - \hat{\beta}), \hat{\beta}] = Cov[b, \hat{\beta}] - Var[\hat{\beta}] = 0 \text{ or that } Cov[b, \hat{\beta}] = Var[\hat{\beta}]$$

Inserting this result in (16) produces the required covariance matrix for the test,

$$Var[b - \hat{\beta}] = Var[b] - Var[\hat{\beta}] = \Sigma \quad (12)$$

The chi-squared test is based on the Wald criterion:

$$W = \chi^2[K] = [b - \hat{\beta}]^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} [b - \hat{\beta}] \quad (13)$$

For $\hat{\Sigma}$, we use the estimated covariance matrices of the slope estimator, in the LSDV model and the estimated covariance matrix in the random effect model, excluding the

constant term. Under the null hypothesis, W is asymptotically distributed as chi-squared with K degrees of freedom (Greene, W.H, 2003).

2.6.2 Breusch and Pagan's Test

This test aims to see whether there are individual/time (or both) effects in the data panel, namely by testing the hypothesis in the form

$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$, or there is no a two-way effect (individual effect and time effect)

$H_0 : c_i = 0$, or there is no individual effect

$H_0 : d_i = 0$, or there is no time effect

We look at a Lagrange Multiplier test developed by Breusch and Pagan (1980), the test statistics is given by

$$LM = \frac{NT}{2(T-1)} \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N e_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T e_{it}^2} \right) - 1 \right]^2 \quad (14)$$

Where e_{it} denotes the OLS residual on the pooled model, e_i denote their sum over t , respectively. Under the null hypothesis H_0 this LM statistics is distributed as a χ_1^2 .

2.6.3. Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge Test

Under the null of no serial correlation in the errors, the residual of a model must be negatively serially correlated, with $cor(\hat{\varepsilon}_{it}, \hat{\varepsilon}_{is}) = -\frac{1}{(T-1)}$ for each t, s . Wooldridge suggests basing a test for this null hypothesis on a pooled regression of FE residuals on themselves, lagged one period:

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{i,t} = \alpha + \delta \hat{\varepsilon}_{i,t-1} + \eta_{i,t} \quad (15)$$

Rejecting the restriction $\delta = -\frac{1}{(T-1)}$ makes us conclude against the original null of no serial correlation.

2.6.4. Pesaran CD Test

Pesaran (2004) recommended a simple test of error cross-section dependence (CD) that is applicable to variety of panel models, including stationary and unit root dynamic heterogeneous panels with small T and Large N . The proposed test is based on an average of pairwise correlation coefficients of OLS residuals from the individual regressions in the panel rather than their squares as in the Breusch-Pagan LM test:

$$CD = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \sqrt{T_{ij}} \hat{\rho}_{ij} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Where } \hat{\rho}_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T e_{it}e_{jt}}{\left(\sum_{t=1}^T (e_{it}^2)\right)^{1/2} \left(\sum_{t=1}^T e_{jt}^2\right)^{1/2}},$$

$\hat{\rho}_{ij}$ is the product-moment correlation coefficient of a model's residuals; e_{it} denoting the OLS residuals based on T observations for each $i=1,\dots,N$. In the case of an unbalanced panel only pairwise complete observations are considered, and $T_{ij} = \min(T_i, T_j)$ with T_i being the number of observations for individual I; else, if the panel is balanced, $T_{ij} = T$ for each i, j . Under the null hypothesis of cross-section independence, $CD \sim N(0,1)$.

2.6.5. Robust Covariance Matrix Estimation.

Wald-type tests is used for Robust estimators of the covariance matrix of coefficients, consistent vs. serial correlation is generally resulted in the context of panel data version. Basically, all types assume there is no correlation between errors of different groups while allowing for heteroskedasticity. All types assume no correlation between errors of different groups while allowing for heteroskedasticity but no serial correlation, i.e.

$$\Omega_i = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{i1}^2 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{i2}^2 & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & \sigma_{iT}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

While “White2” is “White1” limited to a common variance inside every group, estimated as $\sigma_i^2 = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\hat{u}_{it}^2}{T}$ so that $\Omega_i = I_T \otimes \sigma_i^2$, lets a totally general structure w.r.t

heteroskedasticity and serial correlation

$$\Omega_i = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{i1}^2 & \sigma_{i1,i2} & \dots & \sigma_{i1,iT} \\ 0 & \sigma_{i2}^2 & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \sigma_{iT-1,iT} \\ \sigma_{iT,i1} & \dots & \sigma_{iT,iT-1} & \sigma_{iT}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

The latter is, as already observed, consistent w.r.t timewise correlation of the errors, but on the converse, unlike the White 1 and 2 methods, it relies on large n asymptotics with small T.

3. An Empirical Study in Panel data approach

3.1. Novelty of the Model

Panel data methods we can use when both time series and cross-sectional data are available and when only the relationship between the tourism demand variable and its determinants is of interest. We are interested in examining the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) are related to the Number of international Tourist

Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, Tax Revenue in tourism sector, and Total Employment in Tourism sector.

TripAdvisor, the leading travel review site, has ranked the world's best travel destinations of 2018. The site's Travelers' Choice Awards for destinations recognised travellers' favourite destinations around the world. According to TripAdvisor award 2018, the 10 Best Travel Destinations in 2018: 1).Paris, France; 2).London, United Kingdom; 3) Rome, Italy; 4) Bali, Indonesia; 5).Crete, Greece; 6).Barcelona, Spain; 7).Prague, Czech republic; 8).Marrakech, Morocco; 9) Istanbul,Turkey; 10)New York City, USA. This is novelty model in tourism demand focus on the 10 best travel destinations of 2018 and data are compiled from <https://data.worldbank.org>, for the period 1995 to 2017.

After transformation original data used natural log, the panel model represent as:

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Where the variable definitions for country i are:

Y_{it} = Gross Domestic Product (US\$) for country i;

X_1 = Number of International Tourist Arrivals (number of person) for country i;

X_2 = International Tourism Receipts (US\$) for country i;

X_3 = International Tourism Expenditures (current US\$) for country i;

X_4 = Tax Revenue in tourism sector (%) for country i;

X_5 = Total Employment in tourism sector (%) for country i;

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ = Slope coefficient for $X_1 \dots X_5$;

c_i = the unobservable individual effects;

d_t = the unobservable time effects;

ε_{it} = the usual disturbance term which varies across regions and time;

$i = 1, 2, \dots, 10$ (the 10 Best Travel Destinations in 2018);

$t = 1, 2, \dots, 230$ (from 1995- 2017).

R-studio software is used for panel model analysis. To describe the calculation of the panel model where the panel model will be estimated is presented as follows:

Model I :

$$\log Y_{i,t} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model II:

$$\log Y_{i,t} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model III:

$$\log Y_{i,t} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

3.2. Analysis Model

3.2.1. Hausmann Test

In this study we used transformation model with natural log, and then for analysis model, first of all we consider to used Hausmann Test for data.

Table 1. Hausmann Test for Fixed versus Random Effects Model

Model	Statistics Test	p-value	Conclusion
Model I	6.2911	0.2789	Fixed Effects
Model II	12.958	0.01148	Random Effects
Model III	4.0757	0.3959	Fixed Effects

Source : Data Processed

H_0 : Fixed Effects model is used for Panel Model

H_1 : Random Effects model is used for Panel Model

The Hausman Test helps us to decide between the fixed effects and Random effects or to select the model will be used for analysis. In this case, if the p-value > 0.05 then use Fixed effects, if not use random effects.

3.2.2. Breusch-Pagan Test

Summary results of Breusch-Pagan Test is given in the following table 2,

Table 2 Summary results of Breusch-Pagan Test

Model	Hypotesis	Statistics test	p-value	Conclusion
Model I	$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$	286.51	$< 2.2e-16$	H_0 rejected, there is a two-way effect
	$H_0 : c_i = 0$	283.01	$< 2.2e-16$	H_0 rejected, there is a individual effect
	$H_0 : d_i = 0$	3.4932	0.06162	H_0 is accepted, there is no time effect
Model II	$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$	147.29	$< 2.2e-16$	H_0 rejected, there is a two-way effect
	$H_0 : c_i = 0$	142.98	$< 2.2e-16$	H_0 rejected, there is a individual effect
	$H_0 : d_i = 0$	4.3057	0.03799	H_0 rejected, there is a time effect
Model III	$H_0 : c_i = 0, d_i = 0$	427.54	$< 2.2e-16$	H_0 rejected, there is a two-way effect
	$H_0 : c_i = 0$	422.13	$< 2.2e-16$	H_0 rejected, there is a individual effect
	$H_0 : d_i = 0$	5.4077	0.02005	H_0 is accepted, there is no time effect

Source : data processed

From the results of the hausman and Breusch-Pagan test above, it can be concluded that the models will be estimated are presented as follows:

Model I : Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect,

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model II: Random Effect Model with two-way effect (Individual effect and time effect)

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model III: Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect

$$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_4 \log X_4 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

3.3. Model Estimation

Model estimation can be done using the Generalized Least Squares in Fixed-Effects Model and Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) in Random- Effects Model. To specify the models and type of effect from the panel analyzed we have used Rstudio software. Finally, model I is reduced to the best panel model, namely *Model A (Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect)*: $\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$; model II is reduced to the best panel model, namely *Model B (Random Effect Model with Individual effect and time effect)*: $\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$, and model III is reduced to the best panel model, namely *Model C (Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect)*: $\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$

3.4. Diagnostic Tests

For the best panel models that have been reduced (Model A, model B, and Model C) diagnostic tests have been conducted following:

3.4.1. Testing for Serial Correlation

Serial correlation tests apply to macro panels with long time series. Not a problem in micro panels (with very few years). The null is that there is no serial correlation. In this study we used Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for serial correlation in panel model where

H_0 : There is no serial correlation

H_1 : There is serial correlation

Summary results of Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for serial correlation in panel models is given in the following table 3:

Table 3. Summary results of Breusch-Godfrey/Wooldridge test for serial correlation

Model panel	Statistics test	p-Value	Conclusion
Model A	0.51537	0.7728	There is no serial Correlation
Model B	1.7725	0.4122	There is no serial Correlation
Model C	0.7699	0.6805	There is no serial Correlation

Source: data processed

Interpretation for model A: “p-value < 0.7728, accepted H_0 , there is no serial correlation; Interpretation for model B: “p-value < 0.4122, accepted H_0 , there is no serial correlation; and Interpretation for model C: “p-value < 0.6805, accepted H_0 , there is no serial correlation.

3.4.2. Testing for cross-sectional dependence/contemporaneous correlation

The null hypothesis in Pasaran CD tests of independence is that residuals across entities are not correlated or connected. The residuals are tested by Pasaran CD (cross-sectional dependence) and it will be correlated across entities*. Cross-sectional dependence can lead to bias in tests results (also called contemporaneous correlation)

H_0 : There is no cross-sectional dependence

H_1 : There is cross-sectional dependence

Summary results of Pasaran CD test for Cross-sectional dependence in panel models is given in the following table 4:

Table 4. Summary results of Pasaran CD test

Model panel	Statistics test	p-Value	Conclusion
Model A	0.13552	0.8922	There is no Cross-sectional dependence
Model B	-1.359	0.1741	There is no Cross-sectional dependence
Model C	-3.2423	0.001186	There is Cross-sectional dependence

Source: data processed

It can be seen that the model C does not fulfill the assumption that there is a Cross-sectional dependence in the model so that it is excluded from the best possible model for the panel model.

3.4.3. Testing for Heteroskedasticity

Robust Covariance Matrix Estimation can be used for testing heteroskedasticity. We can see that standard errors given different types of HC (Heteroscedsticity), we found that there is no heteroskedasticity in Fixed Effects model and Random Effects Model, is given in the following table 5 and table 6.

Table 5. Controlling for Heteroskedasticity :Fixed Effects

	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_5
HC0	0.1195791	0.07264911	0.06443014	0.08419023
HC1	0.1206327	0.07328920	0.06499781	0.08493201
HC2	0.1215598	0.07366955	0.06550383	0.08550706
HC3	0.1235913	0.07471906	0.06660124	0.08685710
HC4	0.1241640	0.07497062	0.06673373	0.08739503

Source: data processed

Table 6. Controlling for Heteroskedasticity :Random Effects

	(Intercept)	β_1	β_3
HC0	0.3927842	0.08013458	0.06492875
HC1	0.3953712	0.08066236	0.06535638
HC2	0.3965705	0.08097449	0.06557599
HC3	0.4004054	0.08182568	0.06623206
HC4	0.3995587	0.08173095	0.06613156

Source: data processed

4. Estimation Results

It can be seen from the overall results of the analysis above, that models A and B were obtained that met the results of the diagnostic test. To determine which model is best presented through table 7 below

Table 7. Fixed effects and Random Effects models : Estimation results

MODEL A (Fixed-Effect Model with Individual effect):				
$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_2 \log X_2 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + \beta_5 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	Pr(> t)
β_1	0.419731	0.093715	4.4788	1.216e-05 ***
β_2	0.171607	0.071369	2.4045	0.01704 *
β_3	0.543294	0.041771	13.0064	< 2.2e-16 ***
β_5	-0.747976	0.078490	-9.5295	< 2.2e-16 ***
Total Sum of Squares				50.856
Residual Sum of Squares				2.3726
R-Squared				0.95335
Adj. R-Squared				0.95054
F-statistic				1103.48
p-value				< 2.22e-16
MODEL B (Random Effect Model with two-way effect/Individual effect and time effect)				
$\log Y_{it} = \beta_1 \log X_1 + \beta_3 \log X_3 + c_i + d_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}$				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	0.833420	0.225393	3.6976	0.0002176 ***
β_1	0.479763	0.047238	10.1564	< 2.2e-16 ***
β_3	0.606135	0.038210	15.8633	< 2.2e-16 ***
Total Sum of Squares				54.835
Residual Sum of Squares				3.5669
R-Squared				0.93495
Adj. R-Squared				0.93438
Chisq				3262.73
p-value				< 2.22e-16

Source: data processed

By looking at the value of the Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) of each model, where for models A=2.3726 and model B=3.5669, based on the principle of simplicity (Parsimony) that by viewing the minimum of RSS value. It can be concluded that model A is the best model. We can see also, the value of Adj. R-Squared for model A =0.95054 higher than the value of Adj. R-Squared for model B=0.93438. We found that model A: $\log Y_{it} = 0.42 \log X_1 + 0.17 \log X_2 + 0.54 \log X_3 - 0.75 \log X_5 + c_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}$ (The fixed effect model with individual effects) is the best panel model, with values of the unobservable individual effect (C_i) for each country presented in table 7.

Table 7: Ci Value for each Country, the 10 Best Travel Destinations 2018

Countries	France	UK	Italy	Indonesia	Greece	Spain	Czech rep.	Morocco	Turkey	USA
C_i	1.776	1.776	1.839	1.819	1.736	1.573	1.589	1.717	1.826	1.877

Source: data processed

In table 5 we can see for the best model in panel data is model A (Fixed Effects Model with Individual effect), where β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are all significant (t-value > Pr(>|t|)), this implies that the positive effect on Gross Domestic Product (GDP) arising from Number of International tourist arrivals (X_1); International Tourism Receipts (X_2); and International Tourism Expenditures (X_3), although the negative effect on Gross Domestic Product (Y_{it}) arising from Total Employment in tourism sector (X_5), where β_5 is also significant (t-value < Pr(>|t|)) Furthermore, Adj. R-Squared = 0.95054 and F-statistic = 1103.48 (p-value = < 2.22e-16), this implies that all independent variables are adjusted together explain the variable GDP (dependent variable) by 95,054% while the remaining 4.946% is explained by other variables outside the model and all independent variables are statistically significant at a = 5% which means all independent variables have a significant influence on the GDP variable.

5. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Based on the F test, the Number of International Tourist Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, and Total Employment in the tourism sector, have a simultaneous significant influence to The Gross domestic product (GDP). Results of this study shows that the International Tourist Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, and Total Employment in tourism sectors as factors that can explain changes in Domestic Products Gross (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
- 2) Based on t-test, the number of International Tourist Arrivals has a partial positive impact that is significant to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study reveal that the Number of International Tourist Arrivals as a factor that can explain changes in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
- 3) Based on t-test, International Tourism Receipts has a partial positive impact that is significant to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study show that International Tourism Receipts as a factor that can explain changes in The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
- 4) Based on t-test, International Tourism Expenditures has a partial positive impact that is significant to the Gross domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study show that International Tourism Expenditures as a factor that can explain changes in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA.
- 5) Based on t-test, Total Employment in the tourism sector has a partial negative impact that is significant to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Results of this study show that Total Employment in the tourism sector as a factor that can explain changes in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA. Its surprising results that may reveal the possibility of unreported transactions, low payment to increased employment and the black market in the sector that does not reflect the reality of employment contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP).
- 6) Based on Adj.R square, this implies that the Number Of International Tourist Arrivals, International Tourism Receipts, International Tourism Expenditures, and Total Employment in the tourism sector, adjusted together explain the Gross

Domestic Product (GDP) by 95.054% from Paris, UK, Italy, Indonesia, Greece, Spain, Czech Rep., Morocco, Turkey, and the USA while the remaining 4.946% is explained by other variables outside the model.

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